

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**AN INTERVENTIONAL STUDY TO IDENTIFY THE ROLE OF
AWARENESS ABOUT ROLE OF VACCINES FOR HIV/AIDS
CONTROL PROGRAMS**¹Dr Mah Jabeen, ¹Dr Ayesha Adrish, ²Dr Aamna Liaquat
¹Bahawal Victoria Hospital Bahawalpur, ²Shalamar hospital Lahore.**Article Received:** March 2019**Accepted:** April 2019**Published:** May 2019**Abstract:**

Background: HIV is a very dangerous infection. Its ways of transformation to other persons and its avoidance are not well understood to the younger generation.

Objectives: The main purpose of the study was to identify the role of health education for the awareness of the younger generation about the dangerous effects, transformation, and prevention of the disease.

Patients and Methods: This interventional research was carried out at Mayo Hospital, Lahore (February to November 2008). The study was conducted in two segments. The basic information of the students about HIV was identified during the first segment. Students belonging to various classes were included in the study. These were 350 in numbers. Then a lecture was given to the students about the information of communication and anticipation of the disorder. The patients who were present in the first segment were called to enter in the second segment for further analysis after 3 months. 314 students became ready to enter into the next segment. SPSS was used to assess the data.

Results: Average age of the participants was about (17.44 ± 1.28) years. The students having experience of 13 or 14 years were well as compare to 11 and 12 years of age. 314 students were included in the second segment of the study. By joining the second segment the knowledge of the participants enhanced to a greater extent.

Conclusions: It has been concluded that the students must obtain reasonable information about the communication and anticipation of the infection. Students should be asked to discuss HIV and its various symptoms to each other.

Keywords: HIV/AIDS, College Students and Health Education.

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Please cite this article in press Mah Jabeen et al., *An Interventional Study to Identify the Role of Awareness about Role of Vaccines for Hiv/Aids Control Programs.*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2019; 06(05).

INTRODUCTION:

In a most mechanized world, HIV is considered as a main issue of health. In the world, there are almost 33.4 million sufferers of AIDS. 2.1 million Out of this number are younger patients. 2.7 million Persons were found to attack by HIV in the year 2008. 2 million mortalities were also recorded in the same year [1]. About 50% of patients of the AIDS-affected by it before the age of 25 years and their death were noticed within the upcoming 10 years [2]. Most of the patients suffering from AIDS belong to the lower or middle-class society [3]. In Pakistan until now about 97, 400 patients were recorded. This disease is spontaneously increasing in individuals like drug users and male sexual characteristics workers [4].

In the current years, less pervasiveness of HIV was recorded. The dangers of increased HIV chances in Pakistan are due to the involvement of the individuals in high-risk factors, less information about the infection and harmful conduction of blood and inoculations activities. An extra apprehension is Pakistan's geographic immediacy to India, a state that was considered a highly affected country with the AIDS according to the estimation of the World Health Organization [5]. The main source of the transmission of HIV in Pakistan and India is sexual activities. There are some other causes of transfer of AIDS to other persons. The one other factor is the late weddings of males and females. Because of late marriages, premarital sexual activity should be enhanced but the confirmation across the state of enhanced premarital sexual activities is still questionable [6, 7].

The youngsters are engaged in the study and risky activities than focusing on their studies. It was pointed out by the youngsters most of them are able for sexual activities and they were between the child and adults. The question arises in the mind of the youngsters about the testing and health risk actions because of rising cognitive capabilities and communal observations. Recent health was in danger because of some actions. Long-lasting health penalties were observed because of some deeds [8]. A report was published in 2002 by the United Nations. It was noticed in the report that most of the youngsters have no information about HIV/AIDS. They did not know even the protection ways from the disease. Less healthful behaviors were developed by adolescents. They obtain information about the sexual activity from the staring group and cushion books etc. They were sometimes misguided by these sources of information because these are not reliable sources of information [9]. Persons reached the age of puberty about the ages of 15 to 19 were observed

to have more risks of STDs. As a result, 25% of all the HIV patients constricted HIV when they were younger in age [10]. So the main efforts of the World Health Organization and AIDS Prevention Centers to prevent the individuals from AIDS at the young age [11].

13 HIV treatment and care centers of HIV were formulated by National and Provisional AIDS Control Programs. 2819 sufferers of AIDS obtain cure and out of these 1258 are on life preventing antiretroviral remedy. In Pakistan by the grace of God HIV treatment centers were established in each province. Well trained doctors and staff are present in these clinics. NGOs also aided the persons affected by AIDS [12].

Pakistan has found a greater group of youngsters suffering from an infection. And it was expected that many more will be obtained in the coming years [13]. Many difficult problems and decisions are faced by younger generations. They decide some hard actions like school leaving, jobs and accountability for oneself and for folks. In Pakistan, less knowledge is available on the condition of adolescents. So very small substantiations are present to formulate the strategies. To obtain knowledge about HIV in the youngsters this study was organized.

SUBJECTS AND METHODS:

This interventional research was carried out at Mayo Hospital, Lahore (February to November 2008). Total of 350 students entered in the study. A paper of questions was solved by the students to identify the information criteria in the students. The cause of the experimentation was elucidated in front of students.

In the first segment of the experiment, students are identified by asking questions about the manner of conduction and anticipation methods of HIV. After getting information about the knowledge of the students a detailed lecture was given to the students about the awareness of the infection. The lecture was conveyed on power point. After three months of initial experimentation, the similar question paper was filled by those students again. 314 of the prior experiment were added in the second segment of the disease. The various factors affecting the information of the students like communal and demographic changes about HIV were analyzed. The data was gathered by using SPSS.

RESULTS:

The type of study was interventional. The study was arranged in two segments. The gap between the two phases was about three months. 350 students were

included in the first study. The average age of the students was between 17.44 ± 1.28 years. 117 patients were of 17 years of age. The age of 16 patients was about 16 years. 79 patients were recorded to have the age of 18 years. 45 patients were of the age of 19 years and 20 patients were noticed to have the age of about 20 years. Students belonging to various classes and years were added in the study.

162 patients were from 1st year, 101 from 2nd year, 58 from 3rd year and 29 from the 4th year.

71.43% of patients have little knowledge about AIDS. Patients with 13 or 14 years have more information about the infection as compare to the patients of 11 and 12 years of study.

Table – I: Age and class wise distribution of students

Age	No of students	Class	No of students
16	81	1st year	162
17	124	2nd year	101
18	79	3rd year	58
19	45	4th year	29
20	21	-	-
Total	350	Total	350

Patients receive knowledge about AIDS from various sources. Mostly gained information from TV, 8.85 from radio, 20.85% from friends, 8.86% from magazines and 4.28% from health centers.

Only a small number of students know about the causes of the infections. They just know that it is transferable to a partner during the sexual intercourse or by transfer of blood from one person to another. 54.29% said that this is more readily transferable via injections and use of contaminated syringes. 22.29%

are of viewpoint that it can also transmit from mother to its fetus. 52.29% thought that it can also spread by using contaminated food. It is also a misconception of about 65.71% persons that it can transfer by kissing. Some thought that by using the towel and bed of infected persons it can also be transferred. 68.29% are of the point of view that by sexing with a normal healthy person or by the use of condom HIV can be avoided. 59.14% believed that its prevalence can be reduced by avoiding the sharing of syringes and razors.

Table – II: Responses before and after health educational intervention

Questions	Before N = 350	After N = 314
Have you heard about AIDS	71%	90%
Causative agents	4%	47%
Sources of information		
TV – 57%, Friends-21%, Newspaper-9%, Radio-9%, Health personnel's -4%		
HIV AIDS Transmission		
Unprotected sex with an infected partner	61%	89%
Use of injection	54%	83%
Mother transmit HIV to their babies	22%	69%
Transfusion of contaminated blood	57%	91%
The virus does not spread by		
Preparing food	52%	87%
Sharing towels and bedding	39%	84%
Contact with saliva without blood	34%	76%
HIV Prevention		
Sex with a single partner who is unaffected	68%	92%
Use of condom	34%	63%
Do not share razors	52%	82%
Do not share needles	59%	81%

After the first segment patients were asked to participate in the second segment after 3 months. 314 patients of the first segment were added in the second segment. 36 patients of the first segment were not added in the study.

An important betterment was analyzed in the information of the students about HIV. Information about the sources of AIDS arises from 4.29 to 47.14%. It was prevailed by the sexual activity with diseased individuals, by using contaminated syringes and needles, etc. 68.78% said that HIV can also be

transferred from mother to fetus.

In the students after the second segment, development in the communication of HIV was observed. In 91% of patients, it was observed that communication of HIV was done by transfer of blood from infected to healthy patients. A large number of patients about 86.62% identified that there is no transfusion of infection due to the formation of food by hands. It was recorded 83.75% that by sharing beds the infection did not prevail. 76.11% observed that by transfusion of saliva avoiding blood cannot transfer the infection to other persons. By using the avoiding ways the prevalence of the infection was also decreased. The most common preventive measure is avoiding sex more than one persons. It is also important to sex a healthy person having no risks of disease. Condoms should be used to avoid infection. Sharing of razors and syringes of infected persons also enhanced the chances of disease.

DISCUSSION:

The chances of HIV enhanced because of the character of adolescents. The information about HIV was not sufficient in the patients. Basic and significant knowledge was given to the students so they can save themselves from the infection. The younger generation is specially educated so they can challenge and save themselves from HIV in the following period of time. The enhancement of information on AIDS in students lessens the chances of AIDS infection in patients [14]. 71.43% of patients said that they have already listened about the AIDS. A crosswise study was conducted about AIDS and STI in Mirpurkhas. The study was conducted in October 2002. According to this study, 69% of patients declared to already listened about HIV AIDS [15]. Some persons said to gain knowledge about this disease from their friends and through media. It was declared by many patients that they get knowledge about AIDS from the TV. Another similar study was arranged in Rawalpindi. This study showed that 67.54% of patients received knowledge from the TV [16].

The results were less in our study if compared with previous studies. This difference was due to the location of the study. The study in our case was organized in less developed countries. Another main reason for knowledge is close friends. 20.85% of patients told that they got information with the help of their friends. On the other hand, the least role is of health centers. Same consequences were found in the study conducted on the students of the school in Kerman [17]. Patients with greater information and in a higher level of study were more readily aware about

the disease as compared to the low-level students. The information about the modes of communication and shielding measures about AIDS increase in our patients. A restricted study organized in Ukraine also showed similar findings. They found that students of intervention school have more information, certainty, and self-confidence as compare to the students of the restricted school [18]. The certainty of the students enhanced due to health education. In Saudi Arabia, a significant variation in students was recorded after the education of health [19]. The three main causes of transfer of HIV are sex with the affected person, affected blood transfer in body, use of contaminated syringes. This basic information was present in most of the patients.

It is noticed in our study that by operation on media, TV, radio, and newspaper also enhanced the level of information among students about the transmission of HIV by various methods like sex, blood transfer, use of contaminated syringes, from mother to fetus during the transfusion of various food and nourishment, etc. People also know that they can save themselves from such a fatal infection by sex with a single and healthy person, by using condoms and protecting themselves by the use of razors and syringes of other individuals. In Pakistan, people know very little about HIV protection and transmission. Even some students have a point of view that it can be transferred to other persons by using the towel and bedding of infected persons. The little information about AIDS is present in European areas. This is because in European countries its risks are less now. In Pakistan, AIDS is considered as dangerous life-threatening infection but they don't have an idea that it can be transferred from one person to another in various ways. Currently, a study was organized in Belgian about the information of AIDS among the younger generation. Poor consequences were found. Information is spread by the person who knows better about its prevalence and transfusion to their friends and relatives. In spite of these efforts still many individuals are affected by this infection every year. A greater number of students below the age of 15 were reported in the patients of AIDS.

CONCLUSION:

By providing information to public decrease the risks of AIDS. In the recent years, audio campaign plays an important role in transferring the information. This showed relatively positive consequences all over the world. More information should be given to the public so they can save themselves and their dear ones from this disease. Awareness should be enhanced among teachers and parents, commissioners

and families so they can teach the younger generation more clearly.

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